

Digital Marketing and Role of Blockchain in Digital Marketing Industry

Dr. Atul Kumar¹, Dr. Vinaydeep Brar²

¹Associate Professor, Siddhant Institute of Business Management, Pune, Maharashtra, India

²Professor, SNG Institute of Management and Research, Pune, Maharashtra, India

ABSTRACT

Digital marketing is any form of advertising, which utilizes digital mediums to offer goods or services to customers. Therefore, the businesses utilizing the internet for the promotions of their products and services, they are engaged in digital marketing. As we know that nowadays, no company can get success without digital marketing. As all of us recognize, the marketing industry is pretty dynamic and liable to change. By its very nature, it has to evolve to new technologies and consumer wishes. And now, we have a large alternate on the horizon that promises to shake up the advertising enterprise from top to bottom, along with several other industries as properly. We're talking about the Blockchain. The technology has already made a few critical waves within the economic international. This article is an attempt to explain the role and impact of Blockchain in the digital marketing industry.

Keywords: Digital marketing, Online marketing, Blockchain, Advertising, Digital marketing industry,

1. INTRODUCTION

As all of us recognize, the marketing industry is pretty dynamic and liable to change. By its very nature, it has to evolve to new technologies and consumer wishes. And now, we have a large alternate on the horizon that promises to shake up the advertising enterprise from top to bottom, along with several other industries as properly. We are talking about Blockchain. The technology has already made a few critical waves within the economic international, and the Blockchain market is predicted to reach 20 billion bucks by way of the give up of 2024, according to Transparency Market Studies (Suthar, 2018).

You're probably thinking what all the fuss approximately Blockchain is... But let's start from the beginning... what is precisely Blockchain? While the technology may appear too technical for a few to fully hold close, it's a fair concept. Because the authors of the "Blockchain Revolution" explain, Blockchain is a public ledger that shops and distributes statistics. Furthermore, all of us that make use of Blockchain can both use and proportion all its statistics, and consequently, every person performs a function in maintaining the Blockchain updated and transparent.

The system keeps all the data saved in a chain-like pattern and its transcription history in so-known as blocks – as a result the call, Blockchain. The exciting thing approximately the Blockchain is that you could only add information to it. You cannot even copy it or change it. And if someone could try to hack the system or change something, the ledger would be up to date on every user's tool. Thinking about simply what numbers of customers are in a Blockchain, hacking the network is essentially not possible. This makes the technology very comfortable. Now, Blockchain is slowly stepping into the arena of digital marketing. The latest report from Epstein revealed that greater than thirty marketing apps now use the Blockchain technologies to a certain extend.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURTE

Chaudhary and Sharma (2018) explained that improvement in technology through the years has prompted the arena in all components. Big technological improvement has resulted in a series of evolutionary steps as they're the breakthroughs. This advancement can be nicely defined through the example of computer systems and steam engines. The evolution of advertising from traditional advertising to digital advertising is such that the whole international is within the doorsteps of the patron in a single click on.

Saarijärvi et al. (2018) mentioned that purchaser-to-consumer (C2C) digital commerce (e-commerce) is shaping current retailing. Regardless of the reality that a massive amount of C2C e-trade is performed in social media-primarily based platforms (Eg. Fb), it has remained an unexplored location of research, though social media as a business platform can

result in differing patron price and, for this reason, has the ability for customer experiences that lie past the attain of conventional C2C e-commerce actors.

Macchionet al. (2017) analyzed whether the adoption of e-commerce improves business enterprise business, innovation, and operational performance and whether sales internationalization may moderate this relationship. The studies are based totally on a survey inside the fashion industry and a multi-step linear regression model investigating the relationships between e-trade and performance. Effects display that e-trade improves innovation performance but has no sizable relationship with enterprise and operational overall performance.

Bressolleset al. (2015) studied the provider-profit chain (SPC) on e-service high-quality dimensions, on-line patron price (CV) dimensions, e-delight, and e-loyalty in an e-trade context. A total of two,813 net clients filled in an internet questionnaire after completing a detailed assignment on one in every of 28 wine net web sites from seven international locations. The results spotlight the impact of the size of e-carrier best (records, aesthetics, ease of use, security/privateness, and reliability) on the size of online CV (practical, financial, and social cost) as they affect e-pride, which in flip affects e-loyalty.

GarridoAzevedo and Carvalho (2012) explored the deployment of RFID technology in fashion deliver chain management (FSCM). It highlights the contribution of RFID to FSCM, supporting quicker logistics activities, with more products exceptional, cheaper, and with more responsiveness, improving client satisfaction. An inductive idea building method is used to grow a conceptual version for RFID deployment in the FSCM context. Secondary facts analysis from a sample of six businesses helps the identification and dialogue of the real blessings, negative aspects, and barriers felt via companies in a style supply chain while RFID generation is delivered. The logistics sports inside the style supply chain wherein RFID technology is most broadly deployed are delivery operations, tracking of raw substances, semi- completed components, and finished garments, accumulating completed goods, handling methods, tracking boxes, monitoring products from factory to store, receiving operations, monitoring, and sorting of merchandise.

Kim and Forsythe (2010) investigated the elements affecting the adoption of product virtualization generation (PVT) for on-line purchasing small consumer electronics with the aid of applying a changed electronic technology popularity version (e- TAM) and tested version invariance male/woman customers in the standard adoption method. Online surveys are finished by using a US national panel of online buyers. The facts are analyzed using single- and more than one- institution structural equation modeling. The outcomes provide an empirical guide for e- TAM in the context of PVT reputation for online small customer electronics purchasing.

Herhausenet al. (2015) tested the impact of online-offline channel integration (OI), described as integrating access to and know-how approximately the offline channel into an internet channel. Although channel integration has been recounted as a promising strategy for retailers, its effects on patron reactions towards outlets and across exclusive channels stay unclear. Drawing on era adoption studies and diffusion ideas, the authors conceptualize a theoretical model where perceived carrier pleasant and perceived threat of the internet-store mediate the effect of OI at the same time as the internet purchasing level in of clients moderates the impact of OI.

3. OBJECTIVE

To understand the impact of Blockchain in the digital marketing industry

4. DIGITAL MARKETING

According to Convertful (2020) broadly talking, “digital advertising is all advertising activities that use a digital device or the internet.”According to Convertful (2020), the different types of digital marketing can be explained as follows:

- Social Media Marketing
- Content Marketing
- Search Engine Optimization
- Search Engine Marketing
- Pay-Per-Click Advertising
- Affiliate Marketing
- Email Marketing
- Radio advertising
- Television advertising

- Mobile Phone Advertising
- Instant Messaging Marketing

5. IMPACT OF BLOCKCHAIN ON DIGITAL MARKETING

Search engine marketing

To say that Blockchain will disrupt SEO might be an understatement. For starters, paid to search advertising and PPC run through a middleman. As an example, you have the Google display network. But, once all transactions are confirmed through Blockchain, we'll be able to eliminate the intermediary nearly completely. Publishers and marketers can be able to communicate and interact with every other without delay, all while restricting potential frauds.

While it comes to Search Engine Optimization, things also are approximately to change. As groups across the globe begin adopting Blockchain, they'll need to integrate the generation into their websites. Of direction, this involves web developers and SEO specialists as well. SEO professionals will work closely with web developers to solve certain compatibility problems with unique internet platform and content material management systems.

Content marketing

Seeing how you can use Blockchain to protect your data and show the beginning of a product, carrier, or a piece of content material, it has big implications for content marketing. Simply consider a global where you may write a weblog put up, coin a brand-new word, and ensure that nobody claims your work as theirs. With Blockchain, you could effortlessly defend your intellectual property, due to the fact you'll be able to offer a simple proof of starting place. That's now not the most effective way entrepreneurs can use Blockchain to boost their content strategies.

As an example, simply look at ClearPoll, a polling app that makes use of a Blockchain system to record votes. As soon as the votes are cast, they can be tampered with. What's extra, every user can get admission to the outcomes at any time. Even though the app doesn't immediately tie content marketing and Blockchain together, entrepreneurs can buy some POLL tokens and get entry to advances in consumer metrics. In different words, you may use the app to analyze your target demographic closely. Plus, the app also lets you sponsor polls and gain valuable insights and enhance your content strategy, advertising marketing campaign, or maybe business operations.

Social media marketing

Over the previous few years, social media advertising experts have wondered what the position of Blockchain will play in their future enterprise models. The generation will change some of social media networks – inclusive of FB and Twitter - but, that's now not all. In keeping with recent market analysis from Peerity, we're probably going to witness a variety of new social media networks in the next few years.

In theory, social media networks built on Blockchain will be more secure, in view that there's no principal website hosting server. The statistics recorded on those social networks can by no means be deleted, which is a large plus for proponents of free speech. To live one step in advance of their competitors, marketers need to be aware of these networks and put money into them on time. That manner, they'll have to get entry to a large customer base; a lot of their competition will probably miss.

Influencer marketing

As you're approximately the see, even the world influencer marketing will go through a few adjustments as soon as humans start imposing Blockchain technology. As this Bitcoins article mentions, some of the issues that almost each influencer marketing campaign faces are:

- Normal fraud cases
- Inconsistent prices
- Excessive entry barrier

Fortuitously for entrepreneurs, the brand-new generation can potentially address this kind of problem. For starters, Blockchain will dispose of the want for managers within the system, and consequently, allow social media influencers and smaller corporations to attach and cooperate extra without difficulty.

Considering that Blockchain allows you to effortlessly affirm any records – for example, see if a sure influencer has actual fans or now not – and spot whether or no longer you should to paintings with certain influencers. Remaining but now not

least, the digital ledger will guarantee that each influencer is paid for his or her offerings. With fewer scams accessible, marketers will in all likelihood begin spending more money and time on influencer marketing than ever earlier than.

CONCLUSION

Of course, the generation is not perfect with the aid of any approach, because it's still in its infancy. Even the most important Blockchain at the moment – the only that supports Bitcoin – is starting to go through due to its size. However, the technology is still pretty exciting.

What's extra, all of those trends and opportunities we mentioned above indicate that Blockchain is the future of advertising. At the same time as we cannot make certain if Blockchain will triumph over the sector of virtual advertising– one component is for certain – it'll considerably alternate the panorama of advertising over the subsequent few years.

REFERENCES

- [1] Suthar, Sawaram. Will Really Blockchain Redefine Digital Marketing industry? Available at: <https://thenextscoop.com/blockchain-redefine-digital-marketing-industry/>, 2018.
- [2] Chaudhary, Shivani and Sharma, Rasna. "Digital Marketing Revolutionising Fashion Industry: The Synthesis of the theory and practice". *Pramana Research Journal*. Volume 8, Issue 4. pp. 259-266, 2018.
- [3] Saarijärvi, H., Joensuu, J., Rintamaki, T. and Yrjölä, M. "One person's trash is another person's treasure: Profiling consumer-to-consumer e-commerce in Facebook". *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*. Vol. 46, No. 11/12, pp. 1092-1107, 2018.
- [4] Macchion, L., Moretto, A., Caniato, F., Caridi, M., Danese, P. and Vinelli, A. "International e-commerce for fashion products: what is the relationship with performance?". *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*. Vol. 45 No. 9, pp. 1011-1031, 2017.
- [5] Bressolles, G., Durrieu, F. and Deans, K. "An examination of the online service-profit chain". *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*. Vol. 43 No. 8, pp. 727-751, 2015.
- [6] GarridoAzevedo, S. and Carvalho, H. "Contribution of RFID technology to better management of fashion supply chains". *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*. Vol. 40, No. 2, pp. 128-156, 2012.
- [7] Kim, J. and Forsythe, S. "Factors affecting adoption of product virtualization technology for online consumer electronics shopping". *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*. Vol. 38, No. 3, pp. 190-204, 2010.
- [8] Herhausen, Dennis, Binder, Jochen, Schoegel, Marcus and Herrmann, Andreas, "Integrating Bricks with Clicks: Retailer-Level and Channel-Level Outcomes of Online–Offline Channel Integration". *Journal of Retailing*. Vol. 91, Issue 2, pp. 309-325, 2015.
- [9] Convertful. 10 Types of Digital Marketing. March 11, Available at: <https://convertful.com/types-digital-marketing/>, 2018.